

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXIII. Complexes of Cobalt-Nickel-, Copper-, Cadmium-, Zinc- and Mercury(II) with Bis-bidentate Chelating ONOO Donor Azodye Ligands, 5-(3'-Hydroxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxy-1-formylbenzene and 3-(2'-Hydroxynaphthyl-4'-sulphonic acidoazo)ethylacetoacetate

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Bis-bidentate title ligands form binuclear complexes with divalent cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, cadmium and mercury ions. Both the ligands coordinate to the metal atoms through ONOO potential donor atoms. The complexes formed by the former ligand are either octahedral or distorted octahedral in nature but the Co, Ni and Cu complexes with the latter ligand are octahedral or distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry can be suggested for the Zn, Cd and Hg complexes.

The study of metal complexes containing multidentate azodye ligands is of recent interest. Literature survey reveals that no systematic study has been made so far to synthesise polymetallic complex compounds using polydentate azodye ligands. It was thought worthwhile to prepare and characterise di-, tri-, tetra- and polynuclear complexes of divalent transition and non-transition metal ions containing multidentate azodye ligands¹. The present work reports the synthesis and characterisation of two new ONOO donor azodye ligands and their binuclear metal complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The azodyes were prepared by the coupling reaction of diazoniumchlorides obtained from *m*-aminophenol and 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid with salicylaldehyde and ethylacetoacetate respectively.

Preparation of complexes: To the ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides, the azodye ligands in ethanol were added in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting mixture was warmed over a water-bath for 0.5 h. The solution was cooled and pH was raised to 7 by adding dilute sodium acetate solution dropwise with stirring when the metal chelate separated out. The chelates were washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure.

The metal, C, H, N and Cl were estimated by standard procedures. Conductance measurement was made in DMF solutions ($10^{-3}M$). Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made at room temperature by Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Hilger and Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer using $10^{-2}M$ DMF solutions,

and esr spectra of copper(II) complex with $L'H_2$ at room temperature on a Varian E-4 ESR spectrometer. Molecular weight was determined by Rast method using camphor as the solvent.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have the compositions $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$, $[M'_2L'Cl_2(H_2O)_6]$ and $[M''_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$, where $M=Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $LH_2=5-(3'-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxy-1-formylbenzene$; $M'=Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $M''=Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $L'H_2=3-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl-4'-sulphonicacidoazo)ethylacetoacetate$. All the complexes are stable at room temperature and upto 140° indicating coordinated nature of the water molecules. All the complexes are amorphous in nature having high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated² from low Λ_M values ($3.5-5.4 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$).

In the ir spectra of the ligands, one broad band is observed at $3100-3450 cm^{-1}$ (OH), lowered due to O—H...O and O—H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Disappearance of this band in the metal chelates indicates the deprotonation of both the phenolic and enolic OH groups thereby indicating their coordination to the metal ions. In the ligand (LH_2), the bands appear at $1640 (C=O)$, $1570 (N=N)$ and $1270 cm^{-1} (C-O phenolic)$. The bathochromic shifts³ of the former two bands and hypsochromic shift⁴ of the latter in the metal complexes indicate coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through carbonyl oxygen, azo nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms. In the ligand ($L'H_2$), the four principal bands are observed at

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis %: Found (Calcd.)				Mol. wt.	ν(N=N)	ν(C—O phenolic)	ν(M—O)
	M	N	C	H				
LH ₂	—	11.20	63.70	3.90	—	1 570	1 270	—
L'H ₂	—	7.20	50.10	3.91	—	1 580	1 260	—
[Co ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	20.4	5.10	28.60	3.80	12.70	1 540	1 280	470
[Co ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	16.8	3.80	27.70	3.50	10.20	1 560	1 250	460
[Ni ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	20.7	4.90	28.70	3.90	13.10	1 535	1 280	475
[Ni ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	16.9	3.70	27.90	3.50	10.20	1 565	1 255	450
[Cu ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	22.6	4.80	28.20	3.80	12.60	1 530	1 280	470
[Cu ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	17.8	3.70	27.60	3.20	10.10	1 560	1 250	455
[Zn ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	20.7	4.20	30.50	2.60	11.20	1 555	1 240	460
[Cd ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	34.8	4.10	23.80	3.20	10.70	1 540	1 285	475
[Cd ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	31.20	3.40	26.70	2.10	9.6	1 555	1 250	460
[Hg ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	48.20	7.90	18.80	2.30	8.2	1 545	1 280	470
[Hg ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	44.50	3.00	21.10	1.80	7.7	1 550	1 240	455

*LH₂ = 5 (3'-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxy-1-formylbenzene ; L'H₂ = 3-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl-4'-sulphonicacidoazo)ethyl-acetoacetate

1 700 (C=O), 1 580 (N=N), 1 260 (C—O phenolic) and 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C—O enolic). The shifting of these bands to lower frequency regions in the metal chelates shows the bonding of the latter ligand through azo nitrogen, phenolic oxygen and both ketonic and enolic oxygen atoms of the ethylacetoacetate moiety. The presence of coordinated water molecules in all the complexes is indicated⁶ by the appearance of a double hump at ~ 3 400 cm⁻¹ followed by a sharp peak at 840—850 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligand to the metal ions is provided by the presence of bands at ~ 470 (M—O) and ~ 440 cm⁻¹ (M—N).

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibit μ_{eff} values of ~ 5.0, 3.3 and 1.8 B.M. respectively, indicating octahedral structure⁷. The molecular weight data indicate binuclear nature of the complexes.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex chelates exhibit four bands at ~ 8 880, ~ 16 730, ~ 21 475 and ~ 34 320 cm⁻¹. These bands can be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F), →⁴T_{2g}(F), →⁴A_{2g}(F), →⁴T_{1g}(P) and CT transitions respectively, for a distorted octahedral symmetry⁸. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complex show four bands at ~ 9 370, ~ 13 790, ~ 23 350 and ~ 31 240 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), → ³T_{1g}(F), → ³T_{1g}(P) and CT transitions respectively, in conformity with an octahedral symmetry⁹. In case of the Cu^{II} complexes one broad asymmetric band appears at 12 650—12 950 cm⁻¹, characteristic of a distorted octahedral stereochemistry with D_{4h} symmetry. The

broadness of the band may be due to Jahn-Teller distortion¹⁰.

In the esr spectrum of the complex Cu₂L'Cl₂(H₂O)₆, recorded at Q-band, g_{av} value has been found out to be 2.0644 by applying Kneubuhl's method¹¹. This spectrum is found to be isotropic consisting of a single line characteristic of regular octahedral geometry. This type of spectrum may result due to a regular octahedral stereochemistry undergoing a dynamic or pseudorotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion.

The Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with LH₂ are found to be six-coordinated and the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with L'H₂ are four-coordinated with an tetrahedral stereochemistry basing upon analytical and ir spectral data. The following structure can be proposed for the complexes.

with LH₂, M=Co, Ni, Cu, Cd, Hg and X=H₂O ; with L'H₂, M=Co, Ni, Cu and X=H₂O ; M=Zn, Cd, Hg and X=nil.

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